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IN PROCESS INDUSTRY
EEM2023**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

**JAHORINA
MARCH 20-23, 2023**

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ARE MICRO-/NANOPLASTICS THE NOVEL GLOBAL HEALTH CHALLENGE?

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Abstract

In the last few decades owing to the wide application and the increased production of plastics, the disposal of plastic waste represents one of the biggest challenges worldwide. It is predicted that in less than 30 years, around 12 000 million metric tons of plastic waste will be on landfills. Microplastics are classified as plastic fragments less than 5 mm in size, whereas nanoplastics are small particles from 1 to 100 nm. Humans are mostly exposed to micro-/nanoplastics (MNPs) by ingestion of contaminated food and water or by air inhalation. However, the indirect rout of exposure to MNPs via personal care products and clothing could not be neglected. Despite the fact that in last few years MNPs were detected in environmental compartments and biota, the investigation of MNPs in human tissues and biological matrices is still a huge obstacle for researchers due to the serious analytical difficulties regarding sample preparation and analysis. The first evidence of the presence of polymeric particles less than 5 µm in human lung tissue suggested that MNPs accumulates in lungs. Particularly concerning is the fact that MNPs fragments were found in all human placenta portions (maternal, fetal and amniochorial membranes). Only recently, MNPs were detected in human urine samples from six volunteers. In another pioneering human biomonitoring study, quantifiable concentrations of MNPs were measured in blood. Additionally, MNPs were measured in the feces of both healthy volunteers and patients with inflammatory bowel disease. Today, based on in vitro and in vivo studies MNPs are recognized as potentially harmful contaminants associated with increased oxidative stress, inflammation, cytotoxicity and even carcinogenicity. Up to now, it is not enough elicited if the particle size or the MNP composition responsible for MNPs toxicity. Scientists are especially concerned about the fact that MNPs act as vector for both plastic additives and environmental pollutants. Appropriate analytical tools and standardized procedures are crucial for obtaining the human biomonitoring data in order to understand the health risk associated with human exposure to MNPs.

Key words: *biological matrix; human health; microplastics; nanoplastics; polymers.*

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